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DRONE UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE

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IMPLEMENTATION OF UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE (DRONE) SURVEILLANCE FOR VIDEO DATA ACQUISITION

ABSTRACT

This project report shows the drones and possibilities of their using. It was first discussed on constructing the drone, of which its comprise the most important elements which are frame, propellers, engine, system of power the electronic control and communication system. the drone is powered by batteries, which is the major drawback, because it is exhausted after some minutes of flight, causing a decrease drone on the ground. The lithium-polymer batteries are used for powering the drones. This study also discusses challenges, opportunities, limitations, and strategies for the adoption of drones in construction. It assists to contractors, building planners, designers, academicians, engineers, and architects to improve the construction activities for greater efficiency and better performance. It also motivates towards inclusion of technologies. This project report describes an experimental test campaign while using an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and measuring the obtained UAV positions during different flight tasks and in different operative conditions. This paper describes and analyses the measurements of the flight trajectory of the UAV that was performed with the use of a robotic total station (RTS), as compared to the design data and the data recorded in the internal memory of the UAV. Five different test tasks have been conducted. The obtained results have allowed for the assessment of the correctness of task performance as compared to the design and to determine the flying accuracy of the entire UAV set. The proposed set of tasks can be successfully utilized to control the correctness of operation of various types of UAVs and it may be implemented as a universal test to verify the algorithms optimizing take and landings, test flights of the objects, as well as flight planning in various terrain and weather conditions, which will increase the safety of the flights while using UAVs

INTRODUCTION

The earliest recorded use of an unmanned aerial vehicle for War fighting occurred in July 1849, serving as a balloon Carrier (the precursor to the aircraft carrier) in the first Offensive use of air power in naval aviation. Austrian forces besieging Venice attempted to launch some 200 incendiary balloons at the besieged city. The balloons were launched mainly from land; however, some were also launched from the Austrian ship SMS Volcano. At least one Bomb fell in the city; however, due to the wind changing after launch, most of the balloons missed their target, and some drifted back over Austrian lines and the launching Ship Volcano (Alan, 2019)

The Significant development of drones was started in the early 1900s, and originally focused on providing practice targets for training military personnel. The earliest attempt at a Powered UAV was A. M. Low's "Aerial Target" in 1916. Low confirmed that Geoffrey de Havilland's monoplane was the one that flew under control on 21 March 1917 using his Radio system. Other British unmanned developments Followed during and after World War I leading to the fleet of Over 400 de Havilland 82 Queen Bee aerial targets that went into service in 1935 (Alan, 2019).

Nikola Tesla described a fleet of unscrewed aerial combat Vehicles in 1915. These developments also inspired the Construction of the Kettering Bug by Charles Kettering from Dayton, Ohio and the Hewitt-Sperry Automatic Airplane. Initially meant as an un
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crewed plane, that would carry an Explosive payload to a predetermined target. The first Scaled remote piloted vehicle was developed by film star and model-airplane enthusiast Reginald Denny in 1935. In World War II Development continued during World War I, when the Dayton-Wright Airplane Company invented a pilotless aerial Torpedo that would explode at a preset time. In 1940 Denny started the Radio plane Company and more models Emerged during World War II – used both to train antiaircraft Gunners and to fly attack missions. Nazi Germany produced and used various UAV aircraft during the war, like the Argus as 292 and the V-1 flying bomb with a jet engine. After World War II the development continued in vehicles such as The American JB-4 (using television/radio-command Guidance), the Australian GAF Jindivik and Teledyne Ryan Firebee I of 1951, while companies like Beechcraft offered Their Model 1001 for the U.S. Navy in 1955. Nevertheless, they were little more than remote-controlled Airplanes until the Vietnam War.

In Postwar period, in the year 1959, the U.S. Air Force, concerned about losing pilots over hostile territory, began planning for the use of Unscrewed aircraft. Planning intensified after the Soviet Union shot down a U-2 in 1960. Within days, a highly Classified UAV program started under the code name of "Red Wagon". The August 1964 clash in the Tonkin Gulf Between naval units of the U.S. and North Vietnamese Navy Initiated America's highly

classified UAVs (Ryan Model 147, Ryan AQM-91 Firefly, and Lockheed D-21) into their first combat Missions of the Vietnam War. When the Chinese Government showed photographs of downed U.S. UAVs via Wide World Photos, the official U.S. response was “no comment”. During the War of Attrition (1967–1970) the first tactical UAVs installed with reconnaissance cameras were first tested by the Israeli intelligence, successfully bringing Photos from across the Suez Canal. This was the first time that tactical UAVs that could be launched and landed on Any short runway (unlike the heavier jet-based UAVs) were Developed and tested in battle (Wagner, 2022)

In the 1973 Yom Kippur War, Israel used UAVs as decoys to spur opposing forces into wasting expensive anti-aircraft Missiles. After the 1973 Yom Kippur war, a few key People from the team that developed this early UAV joined A small startup company that aimed to develop UAVs into a Commercial product, eventually purchased by Tadiran and Leading to the development of the first Israeli UAV (Saxena, 2013)

Background of Study

Since the beginning of aviation, unmanned aerial systems have been a challenge for scientists and engineers. The first automatic airplane developed by the Wright brothers in 1916 and the drone used by the British Royal Navy for gunnery practice in 1933 serve as examples. The possibility of controlling an aircraft without a pilot has been a challenge, both

from the civil and military point of view. Nowadays, the proliferation of unmanned aerial systems, popularly known as “drones”, is a reality for local policy makers, regulatory bodies, mapping authorities, start-ups and consolidated companies. The number of developed drones has increased threefold from 2005 to present and, additionally, a relevant increase has been observed in the civil/commercial type of platforms, especially in 2012 and 2013. There are many uses and benefits of drones based on their own pilot system (autonomous or remotely controlled) and sensory to achieve accurate positioning and to acquire a great variety of data. By this binomial, drones are an efficient solution for the observation, inspection, measurement and monitoring of territory; ensuring better spatial, radiometric, spectral and temporal resolutions than any manned aerial vehicle and satellite (Gonzalez, 2017).

Statement of Problem

Recently, the world witnessed a significant increase in the number of used drones, with a global and continuous rise in the demand for their multi-purpose applications. The pervasive aspect of these drones is due to their ability to answer people’s needs. quadcopters are providing users with a bird’s eye that can be activated and used almost anywhere and at any time. However, recently, the malicious use of drones began to emerge among criminals and cyber-criminals alike. The probability and frequency of these attacks are both high and their impact can be very dangerous with devastating effects. Therefore,

the need for security, detective, protective and preventive counter-measures is highly required. The target for the surveillance is to investigate the emerging threats of using Quadcopter drones in cyber-attacks, along the countermeasures to thwart these attacks. The different uses of Quadcopters for malicious purposes are also reviewed, along the possible detection methods. As such, this project analyzes the exploitation of Quadcopters vulnerabilities within communication links, as well as smart devices and hardware, including smart-phones and tablets. Moreover, this project presents a detailed review on the drone/Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) usage in multiple domains (i.e civilian, military, terrorism, etc.) and for different purposes. A realistic attack scenario is also presented, which details how the drone is to be performed at simulated attack on a given drone following the hacking cycle. This review would greatly help ethical hackers to understand the existing vulnerabilities of UAVs in both military and civilian domains. Moreover, it allows them to adopt and come up with new techniques and technologies for enhanced UAV attack detection and protection. As a result, various civilian and military anti-drones/UAVs (detective and preventive) countermeasures will be reviewed (Paul et al., 2020)

Recent advancements in drone technology are opening new opportunities and applications in various fields of life especially in the form of small drones. However, these advancements are also

causing new challenges in terms of security, adaptability, and consistency. This research discusses the drone technology, area of usages, citizen multi-objective uses, drones security, protection, and secrecy apprehensions, drone current intimidations and susceptibilities, existing approaches for drone cyber-security methods, security threats to drones and data sources for current literature review. Small Quadcopters are proving to be a new opportunity for the civil and military industries. The Quadcopters are suffering from architectural issues and the definition of security and safety issues. The rapid growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) opens new dimensions for drone technology but posing new threats as well. The tiny flying intelligent devices are challenging for the security and privacy of data. The design of these small Quadcopters is yet not matured to fulfill the domain requirements. The basic design issues also need security mechanisms, privacy mechanisms and data transformations. (Rizwan et al., 2021)

According to Ezeokoli et al. (2016), the Nigerian Construction industry is a well-known late comer to the adoption of innovations compared to other sectors. The digital revolution faced by construction industries at this time is a paradigm shift in the use of technologies, aimed at increased productivity, efficiency, value, quality, sustainability and reduced lifecycle costs. The traditional safety monitoring of construction projects lacks a good number of trained staffs and taskforce. However, lots of safety and security incidents have gone

undocumented. The indigenous construction professionals and client pay little or no attention to safety and security in an average Nigerian construction site making it risky and accident prone. Government policies and lack of enforcement has made the situation worsen in recent times. (okaka, 2020)

Security threats are associated with drones which can be physical or cyber-attacks. It is important to limit drone usage in civilian areas and properties. The negative use of drones is also increasing day by day. This usage also creates problems for the citizens and civilians. Drone owners use Bluetooth or Wi-Fi channels to control their drones in restricted areas. This can lead to financial loss. Drones are used to breach Wi-Fi connections and Bluetooth signals. Such breach causes so many privacy and security concerns for peoples. (Rizwan at el., 2021)

Significance of the Study

Drone technology provides several advantages and benefits for human beings. It helps in day-to-day activities as well as the military and monitoring of weather. However, several privacy and safety concerns are associated with their advantages. Security and privacy breaches should be addressed properly. Recording and image capturing by drones must be done keeping in mind the privacy and confidentiality of people's concerns. For sanctuary and risk examination of drones, several studies are present in which risk associated with it is considered and discussed. It is important to maintain secrecy,

reliability, obtainability, verification, and non-denial possessions above message-passing networks are fulfilled. This can be achieved through AAA procedures and

METHODOLOGY

The Surveillance drone's packaging material, components values and designations use in the implementation of this project. For every parts and components that has been listed or showed merely have its own purposes. Which basically operate base on its own functionality, mode of operation, working principle and cost expenditure. Specification, analytical analysis, features, basic functions and also Technical plans are being explained: The Drones provide construction teams with an Overhead view of jobsites, materials, machinery and people. Contractors are using the Autonomous flying machines to farm, record images and videos that help optimize everything from Grading plans and operations to identifying Differences between as-designed and as-built Site plans. Their usefulness can be enhanced with thermal cameras and other add-ons.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Drone Block Diagram

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Drone Schematic Diagram

PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION OF THE ENTIRE SYSTEM

The subject of Fluid dynamics plays a significant role for design and development of aircraft and drones. This subject consists of working principle of aerodynamics of aircrafts. A sufficient amount of upward force is required to lift the vehicle against the gravity which is names Lift. the force created to move the vehicle or body in motion is called thrust. These forces can be studied using laws of fluid flows Flow pattern around the cross-section of aero foil or *Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)*

propeller is shown below. High fluid pressure at the bottom and low pressure at the top of propeller cause an upward force which is called as lift. This force is responsible for lifting the weight of aero-plane or drone. The amount of lift force depends on the angle of inclination of aero foil or propeller. Based on the principle of **conservation of energy in fluid flow** (Bernoulli's principle, the sum of all forms of energy in a fluid is constant along the streamline When air flows over an aero foil or wing, its velocity increases at the top portion. But the pressure of air decreases. In contrast, the air velocity decreases and pressure increase at the bottom side of blade. The next pressure difference across the aero foil results in an upward force which is called as lift CFD modeling of flow over an aero foil has been important in many vehicular and aero-space industries

Dynamic movement of UAV

Throttle/ Hover:

The up and down movement of drone is called throttle. If all four propellers run at normal speed, then the drone will move down and If all four

propellers run at higher speed, then the drone will move up. Which is called hovering of drone

Pitch: The movement of drone about lateral axis (either forward or backward) is called pitching motion. If two rear propellers run at high speed, then the drone will move in forward direction while If two front propellers run at high speed, then the drone will move in backward direction.

Roll: The movement of drone about the longitudinal axis is called rolling motion in this process If two right propellers run at high speed, then the drone will move in left direction then If two left propellers run at high speed, then the drone will move in right direction

Yawn: the rotation of the head of the drone about vertical axis (either the left or right) is called Yawning motion. If two propellers of right diagonal run at high speed, then the drone will rotate in anti-clockwise direction which refers to the the rotating or swiveling of the head of the quadcopter either to right or left. It is the basic movement to spin the drone. On most drones, it is the achieved by using the left throttle stick either to the left or right. If two propellers of left diagonal run at high speed, then the drone will rotate in clockwise direction.

SYSTEM FLOW CHART

Flow-Chart and Steps for Drone Controlling:

- Step 1: Start
- Step 2: Input controls
- Step3: Motors running

- Step 4: If up then Take Off Else
- If Shutdown then
- Go to Step 8 Else
- Go to step 5
- Step5: Hovering
- Step 6: Recording
- Step 7: Touch down
- Step 8: Shutdown
- Step 9: Stop

Drone Controlling Flowchart

TESTING RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The project constitutes both different types of hardware, components and software for the aims of achieving proper successful operation. In the construction of the system hardware, more focus and examine was given for the purpose of achieving the aims. The software was use to program the basic internals component, with the basic view to achieve logical decision and to be able to control the entire system such the propellers control, ESC motors etc. of the drone. materials

drone materials

TESTS FLY THE DRONE

Illustration of flied drone

Once everything was deemed functional during the test flight, any vulnerable spots that can interfere with circuit board, electronic speed control, or the flight controller were focused on to fine tune the drone. The circuit board is wide open and that could be hazardous. Water, sand, and high winds can damage the drone circuit board when it is flying or when it is arming before takeoff. This damage can

cause the drone to crash or even worse losing control which can lead to a serious injury or property damage.

Designing a cover to protect the circuit board is essential, the dimensions of the circuit board were added to Fusion 360 software to design the cover: four sides of 90-degree angles consist of 53mm long, thickness of 3mm to cover the circuit board with screws half an inch long to secure the cover to the circuit board. Below is a picture of a schematic diagram showing the dimensions of the circuit board cover using the program Fusion 360 which was used to design and print the cover by 3D printer

RESULT

TABLE

How long do it take to fly at different Height:

Table: The video Result:

High t mm	Time Taken Per Battery/lasti ng	Amoun t of video collecte d.	Durati on of the video taken	Size of the video resoluti on
10 mete rs	90%	1	1 hour 13 minute s	800*60 0
20 mete rs	95.%	3	1 hour 3 Minute s	280*72 0
30 mete rs	81%	3	60 Minute s	1280*7 20
40 mete rs	70%	2	52 Minute s	320*24 0

50 mete rs	56%	1	41 Minute s	320*24 0
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Image Result Taken

Result of the image at 10 meters

c, at small gate

b, at big gate

a, at commercial

Result of the image at 20 meters

c, at small gate

b, at big gate

a, at commercial

Result of the image at 30 meters

b, at small gate a, at big gate
at commercial at commercial c,

Result of the image at 40 meters

Result of the image at 50 meters

c, at small gate b, at big gate a,
at commercial.

progressions. Authorization can also achieve by providing access to the control unit of the Quadcopter/UAV. Verification can be obtained by using multi-level authentication using knowledge (specific key), identity verification and biometric verification. Security threats are associated with drones which can be physical or cyber-attacks. It is important to limit drone usage in civilian areas and properties. The important use of drones is also

increasing day by day. the important security threats to drones. Solutions to prevent these threats are also discussed. (Rizwan *et al.*, 2021)

Safety Apprehensions for A quadcopter is tiny, lightweight, and has high mobility characteristics. It helps to monitor criminal activities which are done at a high level of privacy. It can also be used by criminals to perform their illegal activities. Drones can be equipped with dangerous objects to perform criminal acts. Such acts can create damage to civilians. It is a matter of concern to overcome such extremist activities for the wellbeing of peoples. Several terrorist groups can associate armed objects with a drone to perform their illegals activities. Security doesn't constantly deliver protection. There are chances of damage done by the civilians in civilian areas which can result in financial loss. The following list provides the safety concerns in detail. • Minimum safety features in architecture can lead to control Qua usage. This can result in damage and loss. Absence of Administrative knowledge: especially it mainly occurs when people have less knowledge of safety features. (Rizwan *et al.*, 2021)

Existing approaches for drone cyber-security methods for Major security methods for drone cybersecurity are categorized into the following types. Such classification is based on the attacker's aim and purpose. The following section discusses the existing approaches to prevent drone security issues. A. Drone Network Security Several security problems occur during drone flights and

communication with a base station. To overcome such problems, an intrusion detection method was identified which can recognize illegal activities. Intrusion detection methods capture network flow and detect abnormal activities. Several intrusion detection methods are present which are used to analyze anomalies. These methods include rule-based, signature-based, and anomaly-based intrusion detection methods.

B. Drone Information Safety

Drone communication must be transformed into packet data to prevent load on the communication network. (Rizwan *et al.*, 2021)

RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Piotr Kardasz *et al.*, (2016), “carried out research on a project entitled “Drones and Possibilities of Their Using” they introduced drone as Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAV - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle or UAS - Unmanned Aerial Systems) are the aircrafts, which are able to fly without a pilot and passengers on board. Their Drone performed remotely by radio waves or autonomously (with a predetermined route). the Drones do not have a specific size or type of a drive. They are often equipped with accessories used for surveillance and monitoring, in the form of the optoelectronic heads. They categories the most important feature of the drones as, do not need any additional infrastructure to quickly register and monitor a designated area or object.

A significant advantage is the extremely short reaction time when it comes to commissioning

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and preparing the unit for a flight. The precursors of UAVs are aircrafts used primarily in the uniformed services - the army and the police. They mentioned the first countries that started researches on UAVs were the United States, the United Kingdom, Russia, Germany and Israel. They stated the first time unmanned flying vehicle was used by the Austrians in August of 1849. At the time there were used the balloons (filled with explosives) which have been known for almost 150 years and which were used as bombs (According to Piotr Kardasz *et al.*, (2016) they make mention the first creators of drones was Charles Kettering, who is in collaboration with Elmer Sperry, Orville Wright and Robert Milikanem created in 1915, the aircraft named “Kettering Bug”. It was a primitive automatic plane, which on the basis of sensors defined its height (by using a barometer), the distance traveled (based on the amount of engine spins) and the position. In contrast, the first civilian aircraft was produced only in the 80s of the twentieth century in Japan at the request of the Minister of Agriculture, Forests and Fisheries. Public drones differ from military in the size and the drive. They are smaller and they are driven by an electric motor (military are driven by an internal combustion engine). They are mainly used for photographing and filming.

Drone construction

Drone is composed of two major systems:

1. Movement system
2. Control system.

MOVEMENT SYSTEM

Frame: The basic element of a drone is a frame, which should be maximum light. The classification of frame construction is mainly based on the number of arms. The possible solutions of frames construction are shown in Figure 1. Due to the number of arms and the motors used the drones can be divided into:

1. Bicopters – two engines,
2. Tricopters – three engines,
3. Quadrocopters – four engines,
4. Hexacopters – six engines,
5. Octocopters – eight engines.

It is generally recognized that the construction with more arms allows for a more stable flight. The frame is made of carbon cloth 3K.

Propellers and engine: The next components of a drone are engine and propellers. They constitute the main propulsion system of a drone and are subjected to the highest loads; therefore, their durability is very important. The propellers change a torque (derived from the engine) for a work used for lifting the vehicle in the air. Due to the propeller system in relation to the flight direction it can be divided into the following types:

1. + – One is the leading propeller (at least four propellers),

2. X – The most common construction, in which two propellers

are leading (with an even number of propellers),

Figure 1 propellers Sections

3. Y – Three arms stacked in the Y, where one or two arms can be leading,

4. V – Very rare arrangement in which two propellers lead onto outstretched arms,

5. H – A very rare arrangement where the construction is based on the H-shaped with two propellers leading.

In each of the above-mentioned construction can be mounted double propellers (at the top and in the bottom), which significantly increases the strength of the drone, and does not require the addition of another arm. Double propellers mounted on a smaller number of arms increases the strength of a drone allowing more lift capacity and insuring the

parallel engine in case of a failure. Thus, the own weight of multicopter is reduced, the material costs are falling and the drone can carry a heavier load. The double propellers rotate in opposite directions, balancing one other the inertia force. The wings of drones can be divided also on adapted for rotation:

1. Clockwise (CW),
2. Counter Clock Wise (CCW).

According to Piotr Kardasz *et al.*, (2016)., The wings are made of carbon fiber, plastic or aluminum, and are attached to each other by lamination (also used for attaching the drone extremities), which ensures optimum performance between the weight of the entire construction and mechanical durability. Because of the engine and propellers must be replaced as their consumption, the periodic preventive inspections are carried out. The size of the wings is very important. The larger is the diameter; the lower is the speed, which contributes to a reduction of drone volatility. The larger the wing blades, the greater aerodynamic lift generated, also the pressure exerted on the propeller hub also increases and the forces deforming propellers are getting bigger. The bigger are the propeller blades the stronger must also be the engine to cope torque, which is required to propel propellers, into motion. In addition, it is important to balance each propeller before use to minimize vibrations generated by the unequal operation of the system. It is very important to choose the engine and propellers in such a way that drones could for as long as possible to lift a given *Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)*

load. They made use of brush engines, which are often used for building. However, the experiences have shown that using brushless motors improves durability, efficiency and reduces the consumption of moving parts. This allows for longer and less emergency work of the engines.

The electronic control and communication system

In their research they made they use of control system, as a device that will take the responsible of the drone to fly up, down; rotate, for his reaction to the emerging forces and for stability. Most of the control systems are equipped with the same set of sensors with the difference in the speed of calculations and in algorithms used. The control system consists of:

- Flight controller, responsible for machine control capabilities,
- ESC (Electronic Speed Control) –the unit responsible for engine rpm,
- Supplying plate, separating the power supply for regulators turnovers and motors,
- Sim module, which allows the transmission of telemetry data,
- Proximity camera - an element of anti-collision system,
- The numeric keypad to enter the customer PIN codes.

Their Controllers engines are used to ensure maximum performance and the highest level of fail

safety. Controls should be selected, so that their parameters correspond to the maximum current consumption of the motor, which shall ensure the maximal parameters of drives. Some controllers have additional exit type BEC (Battery Eliminator Circuits), thus it is possible to supply the control system with the voltage of 5V and efficiency of 2A. During their designing process of the control system they first pay attention to the correct power to the controller that establish communication by the programmer. In a further step it is needed to include the necessary filtration power (capacitors and choke) and protection of the pin analog-to-digital converter.

They made use of digital transducer as a voltage meter and its conversion into digital form, understandable for the controller. By measuring the voltage at every cell, we can gain information about the battery charge. In their study for controlling the motor rotary speed, a mechanism was used as PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) or pulse width modulation. For which is possible using this method to obtain different average voltage. On their project Bluetooth communication was use between as controller and smartphone with Android operating system. because Android is now the most popular operating system in the world for mobile devices. It is distinguished by openness, small hardware requirements, simple configuration and easy transfer between different mobile devices. This has contributed to the preparation of an application that allows controlling the drone from the level of smartphone. This allows

for data transmission up to 100 m. To start flights control unit must know the location of the machine in space, which allows the measurement module, containing a gyroscope and accelerometer, which communicates with the controller via the I2C bus. The gyroscope allows tracking the flight of the object, and accelerometer allows the drift of the module and determines the absolute point of reference.

Their Drone control was done, by varying the speed of the respective motors. The control algorithm is necessary to stabilize the machine in air. Comparison of military and civilian drones on selected examples. Military drones differ from civil of size and drive. They are bigger and powered by internal combustion engines. Civil drones are driven by electric motors.

i Civil drones: One example is the DJI Phantom Vision 2, which is used for photography and video filming. The mass of the airplane battery is 1160 g. A lithium-polymer cell with a capacity of 5200 mAh for driving the four rotors allows for 25 minutes of continuous flight with with the recording. The control is performed over the air waves with a frequency of 5.8 GHz using the remote control. The effective control range is 300 m, and using signal amplifiers even 1000 m. Thanks to the Wi-Fi module the synchronization the device with a phone or tablet is possible, which increases the possibility of modifying settings for drone in flight, such as the size or resolution of the recording multimedia,

information about the status of the machine (battery status, connection to GPS altitude speed). It is also possible the preview of the camera view “live”, recording and downloading videos and photos during the flight. The GPS receiver with software provides a standalone return to the starting point in case of losing the connection with the controller.

ii Their constructed Drone recognizes areas, where flights are prohibited (proximity to the airport) and inform the controller about it. The heart of the drone is a camera with photos resolution of 14 Megapixels, filming of 1080p, diagonal of the matrix 1/2.3” and the field of view of 110°/85°. Photos are saved in formats .JPEG and .RAW, which facilitates their interpretation. After equipping the drone with a camera of different type and the appropriate software, the camera can be used to map areas difficult to access.

Military drones: An example of the military drones is MQ-1 Predator (M- is a multirole aircraft, Q mark the drones), which belongs to the UCAV (Unmanned Combat Aerial Vehicle). In the apparatus emphasis is placed on tools for observation. There was used the cameras with a very high resolution, thermal imaging and the infrared.

Components of the drone are as follows

- Rotax four-cylinder engine with 115 horsepower,
- Communications antenna Ku-band,
- Two internal GPS antenna and GPS navigation system,

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- Sets of fuel cells,
- Set of cameras and encoders,
- Transmitter, receiver and radar antenna slot.
- **It is part of the whole set which includes**
 - Four drones’ type of RQ-1 or MQ-1,
 - Ground control station usually placed on a truck, which housed the position of the pilot, the operator of sensors or weapons and an antenna with a diameter of 6.1M with accessories.

According to Tiberiu *Paul et al.*, (2019)., carried out research on “The Use of Done in Forestry” As drone was first acquired in 1860 using balloons, which were later replaced by aircrafts in the first and second world wars. Afterwards, the first satellites were launched into orbit around the 1960s for military purposes, and since the 1970s, once with the development of digital sensors, first civilian applications appeared. In recent decades, remote sensing techniques applied in forestry has been given an increased attention, which leads to the ability of extracting important information for forest planning and sustainable management such as the forest structure, composition, volume or growth (Hao, G. F. 2012). At the same time, with the development of sensors, computers and computational techniques, the applicability of remote sensing in forestry has evolved from aerial photography data] to satellite imagery data, which led to different calculations of forest indexes and were up to estimations of forest volume and biomass. Satellite programs like Landsat,

which is still one of the most used remote sensing worldwide program, is commonly used in forestry. And the recent Sentinel 2, which has a higher revisit frequency, narrower bandwidths and finer resolution, is still limited and not suitable for applications where very high spatial resolution is needed, such as individual trees or even leaves, or those requiring a very short period of area revisiting. In this context, the applicability and effectiveness of drones have a great potential in filling the gaps of other data types even if currently forest applications are still in the experimental stage.

On a Research carried out by Colomina, I., and Molina, on a project Entitled “Unmanned Aerial Systems for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing” They made are UAVS Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) which were originally developed in the early last century and after the 1950s, the main application of drones relied in the military field, through reconnaissance or surveillance. In the last decade, drones of different sizes, shapes and capabilities have grown rapidly and have acquired a growing interest in civilian applications, as well as precision agriculture, forestry, biodiversity, meteorology, emergency.

Applications of UAVS in Forestry

According to Colomina, I., and Molina 2014, Remote sensing using drones has a range of benefits such as reduced costs, flexibility in time and space, high accuracy data and the advantage of no human risks. It is important to mention that even though

forest fires’ monitoring and management was one of the first field in forestry that showed the importance of drones in forestry, getting National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the US Forest Service to present a drone that was able to fly up to 24 hours, at the moment the use of drones spread in other more popular forestry fields.

The following will briefly present recent examples of applications of drones in forestry.

Mapping Forests and Biodiversity

On the paper presented by Chianucci, *et al.*, 2016 entitled “Estimation of Canopy Attributes in Beech Forests Using True Color Digital Images from a Small Fixed-Wing UAV.” An application in order to map forest areas was made by Koh and Wich, where a drone was used in mapping tropical forests in Indonesia. The experiment involved a small UAV type aircraft (under 1 kg) with a flight time range of approximately 25 min per flight and a maximum distance traveled per flight of about 15km. The acquired images were assembled after the flights and a land cover map resulted with a spatial resolution of 5.1 cm. Also, shots and videos that caught different human activities, logging, wildlife or flora species were made. Authors suggested that using UAV remote sensing can save time, costs and labor power for these purposes.

In a paper titled “Drones—An Open Access Journal”: an a view of technologies written by Diego Gonzalez-Aguilera and Pablo Rodriguez-Gonzalvez (2016), they presented an advances in **algorithms**

that is supported by mathematics and computer science which have allowed a new achievements in the field of navigation and images processing either from active or passive sensors. Without these advances in processing algorithms, it would be unthinkable to deal with the enormous- amount of information obtained by the sensors. This information must be processed in the shortest time possible whilst guarantying quality. Therefore, the advances in the treatment of large volumes of information (big-data) have also led to a significant advance in the technology of drones. On the other hand, these algorithms have been automated so that they can provide final products guaranteeing an almost total automation of the process: from automatic flight planning and autonomous navigation (autopilot), even under complicated environments, to the generation of quality cartographic products, mainly digital surface models and orthoimages. Another important aspect to consider is the fusion of sensors, which presents a twofold purpose: on the one hand offering robust approaches to obtain data fusion from different sensors (visible, near infrared, middle infrared, thermographic) and on the other hand, attempting approaches for data fusion using different sensors in different platforms. Last but not least, **new applications** will define new market niches in the coming years. Regarding logistics, the integration of drones into commercial delivery networks is already being tested to optimize the trade-off between the mission time and range, and the security and profit. Moreover, medical applications could benefit from a

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rapid response in a cardiac arrest scenario or for the delivery and transportation of laboratory specimens. Regarding disaster assistance, security and surveillance applications, the automatic recognition based on semantic attributes using images or videos will be crucial to provide a real-time response. In addition, nanotechnology could be used to create nano-drones that are very promising for indoor navigation and inspections. Regarding monitoring, some complex infrastructures (e.g., high and medium voltage lines, oil and gas pipe lines, roads, railways, etc.) could be monitored based on drones.

According to Gilles Albeaino, *et al.*, (2005). In the construction of “A Systematic Review Of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Application Areas And Technologies In the Aec Domain” they carried out a concrete on the increase in the integration of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in civilian usage stems mainly from modern technological advancements and the devices’ abilities to accomplish civilian tasks in a quick, safe, and cost-efficient manner. One sector that witnessed tremendous UAV impact is the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry. Among several AEC applications, UAV technology is currently being implemented for building and bridge inspection, progress monitoring, and urban planning. The following review aims at thoroughly classifying all AEC-related UAV applications within the past decade, extending the understanding of the current state of UAV implementation in the AEC

domain, and outlining relevant research trends in this setting. The review follows a systematic literature assessment methodology in which peer-reviewed bibliographical databases were queried, based on specific search keywords, for AEC-related UAV applications.

This study also discusses the technological components (flying styles, types of platforms, onboard sensors) to assist in better developing, integrating, and understanding the technology implemented in the AEC industry. Our search query yielded 228 articles, of which 86 met our inclusion criteria and were therefore analyzed. Seven categories of structural and infrastructure inspection, transportation, cultural heritage conservation, city and urban planning, progress monitoring, post-disaster, and construction safety were identified and fully analyzed in this study. The study revealed that UAV integration in the AEC domain might exhibit equal, if not, higher outcomes compared to conventional methods as to time, accuracy, safety, and costs. In terms of technology, the control styles reported were mostly autonomous and manual. Rotary wing vehicles were the predominant type of platforms in the literature. Of the rotary wing type, quadcopters were most commonly employed. Readily available, or “off the-shelf” video recording cameras and thermal cameras were most frequently mounted on UAVs, followed by LiDAR and laser scanning devices. Other sensors

included Radio Frequency Identification and Ultrasonic Beacon System. The outcome of this study would benefit both AEC researchers and professionals to recognize the potentials of UAVs and understand the requirements and challenges for their successful integration.

They categories Seven distinct categories of UAV applications in the AEC domain were identified by the authors to provide a framework for discussing prior work. These categories (see Table 2) are not presented as a statement of fact, but rather as the authors’ interpretation of the applications found across the searched publications. They serve as a structure, around which the review of prior work is organized and discussed. Each of the seven categories was intended to be exclusive. That is, an example of a UAV application should fit in one and only one category. These categories were: structural and infrastructure inspection, transportation, cultural heritage conservation, city and urban planning, progress monitoring, post-disaster, and construction safety. Applications that described road condition assessment or maintenance inspection were labelled as structural and infrastructure inspection; otherwise, they were categorized under transportation. Articles discussing damage assessment of buildings or structures affected by disastrous events were considered as reporting post-disaster applications.

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